

MOLECULAR GENETIC PREDICTORS OF THERAPY EFFICIENCY FOR RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS: PREVALENCE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF TNF, IL-6, AND STAT3 GENE POLYMORPHISMS

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Relevance. Genetic predisposition plays a key role in the pathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis, determining individual characteristics of the inflammatory response and sensitivity to pharmacotherapy. Polymorphisms in genes encoding key immune response regulators can significantly influence the severity of the disease, the rate of development of destructive changes, and the response to both basic and biological therapy. In Uzbekistan, data on the prevalence and clinical significance of genetic variants in patients with rheumatoid arthritis are virtually nonexistent, necessitating specialized research to establish a scientific basis for personalized treatment.

The aim of the work was to study the prevalence of polymorphisms of the TNF gene 308 G/A, IL-6 gene 174G/C and rs 4796793 STAT3 in patients with rheumatoid arthritis, as well as to assess their role in the course of the disease and predict the effectiveness of sDMARDs, bDMARDs and tsDMARDs.

Material and methods. The study was conducted at the Practical Medical Center for the Study of Rheumatoid Arthritis and the Shox International Hospital. The genetic and molecular study involved 150 patients with rheumatoid arthritis and 30 healthy individuals. Genotyping was performed using polymerase chain reaction (PCR) with specific primers and amplification conditions. Treatment effectiveness was assessed using standard clinical and laboratory criteria, including disease activity indices, acute phase dynamics, and instrumental data.

Results. For the first time in the republic, the prevalence of the studied polymorphisms was determined in a cohort of patients with rheumatoid arthritis. Significant associations were identified between the genotypes of TNF 308 G/A, IL-6 174G/C, and STAT3 rs 4796793 and clinical disease activity, the rate of progression of erosive lesions, and levels of systemic inflammation. Carriers of certain allelic variants were shown to exhibit different rates of achieving clinical remission and the depth of response to biological and targeted therapy. Genetic mutations allow for a sufficiently reliable prediction of the effectiveness of disease-modifying and biological drugs, paving the way for their use as molecular predictors of therapeutic response.

Conclusion. Polymorphisms of the TNF, IL-6, and STAT3 genes are promising genetic markers for stratifying patients with rheumatoid arthritis and individualizing treatment strategies. Their identification in clinical practice may improve the accuracy of treatment outcome prediction and reduce the incidence of treatment failure.